

Reference List for the Entry: Fälschung in Richtung niedriger bzw. hoher Testwerte [faking low scores, faking high scores]

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This document contains the full reference list from the encyclopedia entry “Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2019). Fälschung in Richtung niedriger bzw. hoher Testwerte. In M. Wirtz (Hrsg.), *Dorsch – Lexikon der Psychologie* (19. überarb. Aufl., S. 584). Hogrefe.” The original text is not included for copyright reasons. The reference list is provided here separately to help researchers find the cited works more easily.

References

1. Röhner, J., Schröder-Abé, M. & Schütz, A. (2011). Exaggeration is harder than understatement, but practice makes perfect! Faking success in the IAT. *Experimental Psychology*, 58, 464-472. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1618-3169/a000114>